

First rehabilitation and services' optimal allocation.

What works best for persons with SCI?

Cumulative thesis submitted for the degree of
Ph.D. in Health Sciences at the Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine
University of Lucerne

Included Papers in the Cumulative Thesis

Paper I

Utilization and features of rehabilitation and health services for persons with spinal cord injury

Status: Published

Available at: [10.23736/S1973-9087.24.08391-6](https://doi.org/10.23736/S1973-9087.24.08391-6)

Paper II

Effective and efficient rehabilitation. What works best for persons with SCI during (sub)acute phase of rehabilitation?

Status: Published

Available at: [10.1016/j.arrct.2025.100532](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arrct.2025.100532)

Paper III

Cost-effectiveness of (sub)acute rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury: a retrospective cohort analysis

Status: Accepted, 08.05.2026

presented by Stefan Metzger

00-713-511

Lucerne, 2026

Submitted on: 04.02.2026

First reviewer: Prof. Diana Pacheco Barzallo

Second reviewer: Assistant Prof. Adrian Martinez de la Torre

License: [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17199947](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199947)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	1
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	2
CHAPTER 1 - Introduction	3
1. Background and Motivation	3
2. Research Objectives and Structure	6
2.1. Research Objectives.....	6
2.2. Structure of the Dissertation.....	7
3. Positioning of the Dissertation within the Existing Literature	8
4. Data Sources and Methodological Approach	9
4.1. Data Sources.....	9
4.2. Methodological Approach	10
CHAPTER 2 – Services Utilization	12
CHAPTER 3 – Effectiveness of Rehabilitation	13
CHAPTER 4 – Cost-Effectiveness of Rehabilitation	14
CHAPTER 5 – Discussion and Conclusion	15
1. Main Findings	15
1.1. Services Utilization	15
1.2. Effectiveness of Rehabilitation.....	15
1.3. Cost-Effectiveness of Rehabilitation.....	16
1.4. Summary of Key Insights.....	17
2. Limitations and Future Research	18
3. Conclusion	19
Bibliography	20

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The driving force behind my PhD project was a clear mission: to demonstrate that specialised rehabilitation for individuals with a spinal cord injury or disease (SCI/D) significantly improves functional health and ultimately enhances participation in society. It is a privilege to pursue a mission that benefits people facing considerable challenges, but this would not be possible without the support of those who make such work attainable. First and foremost, I would like to express my profound gratitude to my family, especially my wife Nicole. Her unwavering support and her constant reminders of what truly matters have sustained me throughout this journey.

I am also deeply grateful to the person who believed that completing a PhD alongside a demanding professional role was possible — and who shared this mission wholeheartedly. Thank you, Dr Hans Peter Gmünder, for your commitment and advocacy. My sincere thanks also go to the management of the Swiss Paraplegic Foundation (Prof. Gerold Stucki and Mirjam Brach) for their trust and for enabling the launch of this project.

Over these past years, balancing family life, professional responsibilities, and PhD studies would not have been possible without a strong team behind me. Together, we have overcome many challenges, including managing the impact of the pandemic on the Swiss Paraplegic Centre, implementing a new organisational structure, introducing SwissDRG for paraplegia in early 2024, transitioning from TARMED to TARDOC and ambulatory flat rates, and much more besides. I would like to express my heartfelt thanks to my team and to my supervisor, Luca Jelmoni, whose unwavering support made this endeavour possible.

I would especially like to acknowledge the people I affectionately refer to as my 'angels'. When I started this PhD, I felt completely lost. The statistical knowledge I had acquired at university was buried under years of professional experience, and re-entering the scientific world presented a whole host of challenges. However, thanks to the immense emotional and academic support of everyone in the Health Economics Group at the Swiss Paraplegic Foundation, my project gradually gained momentum. Whenever I needed guidance, the team was there. My deepest thanks go to my supervisor, Prof Diana Pacheco Barzallo, as well as to Drs Ana Conda and Boris Polanco. Without your support, I would still be at the starting line.

I would also like to thank my other co-authors, PD Dr Inge Eriks Hoogland and Prof Armin Gemperli, for their critical yet constructive feedback, which helped to sharpen and clarify the research findings. I may have gained a few more grey hairs, but I owe you much more than that in terms of insight and academic growth.

Finally, I am delighted that this PhD work will continue within the SNF-funded Smart Rehab project, enabling us to further this mission.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AIS	American Spinal Injury Association Impairment Scale
CHF	Swiss francs
DRG	Diagnosis-related groups
GAM	Generalised additive models
ISNCSCI	International Standards for Neurological Classification of Spinal Cord Injury
KVG	Swiss Health Insurance Act
LCA	Latent class analysis
LOS	Length of stay
SCIM	Spinal Cord Independence Measure III
SCI/D	Spinal cord injury and disease
SPC	Swiss Paraplegic Centre
STROBE	International reporting standards for observational rehabilitation research
XAI	Explainable artificial intelligence

CHAPTER 1 - Introduction

1. Background and Motivation

Global healthcare spending continues to rise, with average health expenditure across OECD countries exceeding 9 % of GDP in 2022 (1). Simultaneously, the need for rehabilitation has expanded substantially, with more than 2.4 billion people now requiring rehabilitation services worldwide—a 63 % increase since 1990, largely driven by the growing burden of chronic conditions within an ageing population, which implies more people require care for extended periods of time (2). These developments intensify the pressure on health systems to cope with increasing care needs and to deliver services that are both effective and economically sustainable.

Rehabilitation is one of the five core health strategies recognised by the World Health Organization, alongside health promotion, prevention, curative care and palliative care (3). Unlike the other strategies, rehabilitation explicitly focuses on people's functioning, considering what individuals can achieve in their daily lives despite health conditions. As such, it directly addresses what matters most to people. From a sustainability perspective, rehabilitation is crucial because, by maintaining or restoring independence for as long as possible, it supports the long-term viability of health systems and the resilience of broader social systems.

Established health economic frameworks, such as cost-effectiveness analysis, can guide resource allocation (4-7). However, in the field of rehabilitation, these frameworks are still not well defined, are applied inconsistently, and are difficult to benchmark (8). Current research highlights that the cost-effectiveness of rehabilitation interventions is often unclear (9), limiting the ability of healthcare providers and policymakers to make evidence-based decisions.

Spinal cord injury and disease (SCI/D) is one of the most complex and resource-intensive conditions in the field of rehabilitation medicine. Individuals with SCI/D face severe functional limitations and require intensive rehabilitation and long-term support and follow-up (10). Although SCI/D is relatively rare, its incidence is projected to increase due to demographic ageing and the rising prevalence of fall-related injuries (11). Lifetime expenditures for SCI/D exceed 1 million Swiss francs (CHF) per person, and subacute rehabilitation costs alone range between 15,000 and 800,000 CHF in international studies (12, 13). These characteristics make SCI/D an ideal condition for analysing the clinical, organisational, and economic aspects of rehabilitation (14, 15).

Importantly, the (sub)acute rehabilitation phase following SCI/D is exceptionally intensive, perhaps only comparable to rehabilitation after a severe stroke, and is often

triggered by a sudden traumatic event that has a significant impact on a patient's physical abilities and mental well-being. Patients must rapidly adapt to profound changes in mobility and independence, so they receive a wide range of closely coordinated interventions aimed at restoring and supporting functional capacity. This highly structured setting provides an excellent opportunity to examine how rehabilitation works, how effective it is in improving functioning and how efficiently resources are used in the real world. As functioning is the primary target of rehabilitation, substantial heterogeneity across injury severity, comorbidities, and recovery trajectories must be explicitly accounted for when analysing outcomes and service provision. The (sub)acute rehabilitation phase begins immediately after injury and continues until hospital discharge (16). In Switzerland, this phase is delivered in specialised centres using standardised assessment protocols and interdisciplinary treatment frameworks (17, 18). This structured, early phase reinforces why SCI/D rehabilitation offers such a unique opportunity to study service allocation, treatment effects and efficiency under controlled yet clinically authentic conditions.

Figure 1. The (sub)acute rehabilitation of people with SCI/D

While much is known about the clinical course of SCI/D (19), considerably less is understood about how service provision relates to functional outcomes and costs (20). Functional independence—the core goal of SCI/D rehabilitation—is best captured using the Spinal Cord Independence Measure III (SCIM III), a validated, sensitive instrument specifically developed for SCI/D (21). However, there is little evidence on how different utilization of rehabilitation services influence improvements in SCIM III, or how these improvements relate to the costs incurred. At the same time, routine clinical and

administrative data are a powerful yet underused resource for understanding real-world practice. These data provide detailed information on the rehabilitation services delivered, their intensity, the patients receiving them, and the outcomes achieved. Despite their potential, routine data are rarely used to systematically examine service allocation, functional gains and cost-effectiveness in SCI/D rehabilitation. Given the rising demand for rehabilitation services, increasing financial pressures and persistent uncertainty surrounding optimal allocation of services, there is clearly a need for comprehensive, data-driven analyses linking service patterns, outcomes and costs.

In addition to the global and scientific importance of this topic, I am motivated to undertake this dissertation by my professional experience. In my role as Head of Performance Management at the Swiss Paraplegic Centre (SPC), I negotiate inpatient rehabilitation tariffs with health and accident insurers. These negotiations require transparent, data-driven evidence that specialised SCI/D rehabilitation meets the statutory criteria of the Swiss Health Insurance Act (KVG): cost-effectiveness, appropriateness, and clinical effectiveness. Qualitative arguments alone are insufficient; robust empirical evidence is essential to demonstrate the value of specialised care. Given the increasing demand for rehabilitation services, reimbursement decisions are becoming ever more challenging. Therefore, generating objective, scientifically grounded evidence is crucial to ensure that patients receive optimal, high-quality care without facing financial hardship. It is ultimately the need for such evidence that has inspired me to pursue this doctoral research, reflecting my commitment to ensuring that rehabilitation remains clinically meaningful and demonstrably efficient.

2. Research Objectives and Structure

This dissertation aims to identify the most effective and efficient way to allocate rehabilitation services during the (sub)acute phase of SCI/D. This requires an analysis of the interplay between service provision, patient characteristics, functional improvement outcomes and financial resources.

2.1. Research Objectives

The following three research objectives were formulated to systematically investigate how rehabilitation services are allocated, how they translate into functional improvement, and how efficiently these outcomes are achieved within (sub)acute SCI/D rehabilitation:

1. Describe the allocation of rehabilitation services during (sub)acute SCI/D rehabilitation.

This includes analysing the intensity, severity, and distribution of rehabilitation services across therapeutic, nursing, and diagnostic disciplines, and identifying how these vary according to patient and injury characteristics. In this context, severity refers to the total amount of service provided. Intensity reflects the rate at which services are delivered during the rehabilitation period.

2. Analyse and estimate the relationship between service provision and functional improvement.

This involves determining which services and service intensities contribute most to functional gains, and whether certain patient groups benefit more from specific types of service allocation.

3. Analyse the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of inpatient rehabilitation.

This objective links total rehabilitation costs with functional outcomes, evaluates efficiency in terms of gains per cost unit, and identifies patient profiles with distinct cost–outcome patterns.

Together, these objectives support the central goal of determining optimal service configurations that maximise independence while ensuring the efficient and equitable use of rehabilitation resources.

2.2. Structure of the Dissertation

To address these objectives, the dissertation is structured into three interconnected parts:

- **Part I – Service allocation:** A detailed examination of rehabilitation service utilization patterns.
- **Part II – Rehabilitation effectiveness:** Analysis of Δ SCIM III (SCIM at discharge minus SCIM at admission) and its relationship to service provision.
- **Part III – Cost-effectiveness and efficiency:** Evaluation of cost–outcome relationships and identification of efficient patient subgroups.

Figure 2. From service allocation to cost-effectiveness and efficiency

This structure provides an integrated, stepwise understanding of how rehabilitation services create value for patients and the healthcare system.

3. Positioning of the Dissertation within the Existing Literature

The existing literature on SCI/D rehabilitation highlights substantial variability in service provision, functional recovery and economic outcomes. Previous research has shown that rehabilitation service use differs markedly across injury groups and patient characteristics, with therapy intensity and nursing demands closely linked to clinical severity (22-24). Likewise, studies examining functional outcomes consistently report heterogeneous recovery trajectories, influenced by lesion characteristics, demographic factors and comorbidity burden (25, 26). At the same time, economic evaluations in rehabilitation remain inconsistent, with limited methodological consensus and considerable uncertainty regarding cost-effectiveness across patient subgroups—an issue that also appears in the broader health-economics literature (8, 9, 27).

Despite these advances, there is a lack of studies that examine utilisation, functional improvement and economic performance within a unified, data-driven analytical framework. Existing research typically addresses these dimensions in isolation, making it difficult to understand how service patterns, patient characteristics and outcomes interact in practice. This fragmentation underscores the need for integrated approaches capable of capturing the complexity of rehabilitation pathways, especially given increasing emphasis on transparency, equity and efficiency in health-system performance.

This dissertation contributes to filling this gap by integrating service utilisation, functional improvement and cost-effectiveness within a single empirical framework using routinely collected clinical data. Building on prior work, it applies compound-risk modelling, generalised additive models for effectiveness estimation and stratified cost-effectiveness analyses. In addition, it introduces patient-profile segmentation through latent class analysis to more precisely capture heterogeneity in rehabilitation needs and outcomes. Together, these methodological innovations provide a more comprehensive understanding of how rehabilitation services generate value, how outcomes differ across clinical subgroups and how more targeted, efficient and equitable rehabilitation strategies can be developed.

4. Data Sources and Methodological Approach

The present dissertation is based on routinely collected clinical, administrative, and economic data from the SPC in Nottwil, covering the period from 2017 to 2020. The SPC is the largest of four specialised SCI clinics in the country and admits approximately 1000 patients with SCI/D annually, of whom about 150 undergo (sub)acute rehabilitation (28). The utilisation of routinely collected healthcare data has been identified as a robust and reliable foundation for health services research and quality monitoring (29, 30). The study was formally approved by the regional medical ethics committee of northwest and central Switzerland (Project-ID2023-04). All participants involved in the study provided consent for the anonymized use of their data for research purposes and were given the option to opt out.

4.1. Data Sources

The dataset includes the following components, in line with international reporting standards for observational rehabilitation research (STROBE):

- Patient characteristics: age, sex, etiology (traumatic, non-traumatic), injury group (high-level tetraplegia (injury level: C1–C4, AIS grade A–C), low-level tetraplegia (C5–C8 AIS A–C), paraplegia (TH1–S5 AIS A–C), and AIS D regardless of injury level), comorbidities and insurance status (accident insurance, mandatory health insurance, or others). Neurological severity was documented according to International Standards for Neurological Classification of Spinal Cord Injury (ISNCSCI) definition and AIS classification (31, 32).
- Functional outcomes: SCIM III scores at admission and discharge, including the domains of self-care, respiratory/sphincter management and mobility. SCIM III is a validated and reliable measure of functional independence in SCI/D and recommended for outcome monitoring in rehabilitation (19, 21).
- Service utilization: therapy minutes (physiotherapy, occupational therapy and speech therapy), nursing minutes, tax-point-based services (psychology and other therapies), and diagnostic services (imaging and laboratory measured in CHF). Detailed documentation of treatment time is essential for linking rehabilitation content to outcomes (22, 23).
- Length of stay (LOS): total inpatient days. LOS is recognised as a quality indicator in WHO Routine Health Information Systems (33).
- Costs: calculated according to REKOLE® and Swiss DRG standards, ensuring comparability and compliance with Swiss hospital costing guidelines (34, 35).

4.2. Methodological Approach

The analytical strategy reflects the three core objectives of the dissertation.

a. Descriptive analyses

Patient characteristics, service utilization (severity and intensity), LOS, outcomes, and costs were summarised using descriptive statistics. Group differences were assessed using Kruskal–Wallis and chi-square tests, in line with common analytical practice in SCI/D rehabilitation research (22, 36).

b. Service allocation modelling

To examine how services are allocated across patient groups:

- Compound Poisson risk models were used to estimate service severity (LOS × intensity). Compound-risk models are widely applied for representing combined duration–intensity burdens in healthcare and long-term care analytics (37).
- Gamma generalised linear models with log-link functions were applied to model daily service intensity. Gamma-family models are suitable for highly skewed, positive-only utilisation data (38, 39).

c. Effectiveness modelling

Rehabilitation effectiveness was defined as the change in functional independence:

$$\Delta SCIM = SCIM_{discharge_i} - SCIM_{admission_i}$$

Generalised additive models (GAM) were used to estimate how $\Delta SCIM$ varies with service use while accounting for nonlinearities and confounding patient characteristics. GAMs are well-established tools for estimating smooth functional relationships in clinical and health-services research (40). The selection of SCIM III as the primary outcome is supported by its strong measurement properties (19, 21) and its widespread use in SCI/D outcome studies (25).

d. Cost-effectiveness and efficiency analysis

The economic evaluation consisted of:

- Cost-effectiveness planes, constructed by plotting total costs against functional improvement. This visualisation approach follows established conventions in economic evaluation (4, 27) and is also recommended for rehabilitation analyses (41).
- Logistic regression to identify factors predicting assignment to the “efficient” quadrant (above-average improvement at below-average cost).

- Marginal effects analysis to quantify the change in efficiency probability with respect to costs and patient-profile characteristics, a method frequently used in rehabilitation cost-effectiveness studies (42).

e. Patient profiling

Latent class analysis (LCA) was applied to SCIM III subdomain scores at admission to identify functionally distinct patient subgroups. LCA is a recommended method for segmenting heterogeneous clinical rehabilitation populations into more homogeneous subprofiles (43, 44).

To validate subgroup separation, t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding was used for visualising high-dimensional functional data, a standard technique in modern machine-learning-supported health research (45). This approach enables subgroup-specific analysis of service patterns, improvements, and cost-effectiveness — aligned with current perspectives on precision rehabilitation (46).

CHAPTER 2 – Services Utilization

Utilization and features of rehabilitation and health services for persons with spinal cord injury

[10.23736/S1973-9087.24.08391-6](#)

CHAPTER 3 – Effectiveness of Rehabilitation

Effective and efficient rehabilitation. What works best for persons with SCI during (sub)acute phase of rehabilitation?

[10.1016/j.arrct.2025.100532](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arrct.2025.100532)

CHAPTER 4 – Cost-Effectiveness of Rehabilitation

Cost-effectiveness of (sub)acute rehabilitation services for spinal cord injury: a retrospective cohort analysis

Submitted 08.01.2026

CHAPTER 5 – Discussion and Conclusion

1. Main Findings

This dissertation aimed to examine the provision, outcomes and economic performance of (sub)acute rehabilitation for individuals with SCI/D, using routinely collected clinical and administrative data. The findings provide a structured and empirically grounded understanding of how specialised SCI/D rehabilitation operates in practice by applying a coherent analytical framework spanning utilisation patterns, functional improvement, and cost-effectiveness. The relevance of such real-world evidence has been highlighted in recent rehabilitation research, which emphasises the growing need for efficient, data-driven approaches to managing increasingly complex care pathways (2, 47).

1.1. Services Utilization

There were marked differences in service utilisation across patient and injury characteristics. Individuals with higher functional dependency at admission received substantially more intensive nursing and occupational therapy. This mirrors long-established evidence demonstrating that treatment intensity correlates strongly with clinical complexity in SCI/D rehabilitation (22, 23). Such patterns reinforce the notion that rehabilitation resource allocation is inherently need-based and shaped by functional severity, as also reflected in the SCIRehab project's consistent findings on therapy time differentials across injury groups (24).

Despite substantial day-to-day variability in service delivery, the total amount of services received by discharge showed convergence within clinically similar groups. This aligns with prior research indicating that therapy programmes, although individually tailored, ultimately follow structured clinical pathways that drive alignment in total service exposure. Such consistency reflects international recommendations for standardised rehabilitation delivery in SCI/D systems of care (17).

1.2. Effectiveness of Rehabilitation

Rehabilitation for persons with SCI is effective, as it showed clinically significant improvements in functional independence across all examined subgroups. Changes in SCIM III scores varied according to lesion severity, age, etiology and comorbidity burden, confirming established determinants of rehabilitation outcomes and aligning with international evidence on functional recovery in SCI/D (25, 26).

Notably, greater service intensity did not consistently result in greater functional improvement. Evidence from broader rehabilitation literature similarly shows that increased

therapeutic input does not uniformly translate into proportional functional gains and that diminishing marginal returns emerge at higher treatment doses (48). This observation is consistent with patterns reported across diverse inpatient rehabilitation contexts, including hip fracture and stroke, where additional resources frequently yield smaller incremental benefits (41).

Together, these findings underscore the importance of aligning service intensity with clinical need rather than assuming linear relationships between input and outcome.

1.3. Cost-Effectiveness of Rehabilitation

The cost-effectiveness analysis revealed a non-linear relationship between total rehabilitation costs and functional improvements. Patients with moderate costs and moderate-to-high functional gains exhibited the highest likelihood of achieving cost-effective outcomes, consistent with economic theory and empirical observations across rehabilitation studies (9, 27).

Patients with complex cervical injuries incurred substantially higher costs due to elevated care needs; however, they still achieved meaningful improvements. Prior research indicates that even modest functional gains—such as those captured by small increases in SCIM—can translate into major improvements in independence and long-term care requirements for individuals with severe SCI (19, 49). This supports the interpretation that lower absolute effectiveness values in highly dependent individuals do not reflect inefficiency but rather the inherent challenges and clinical value of treating such complex cases.

The identification of distinct efficiency profiles, differentiated by injury severity, functional status, and service utilisation patterns, aligns with emerging precision rehabilitation frameworks, which advocate tailoring interventions and resource deployment to patient subgroups (46). It also echoes systematic calls for stratified economic evaluation methodologies in rehabilitation science (8, 50).

1.4. Summary of Key Insights

Three central insights emerge across utilisation, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness:

1. Resource allocation is structured yet responsive to patient need.

Consistent patterns of service use within injury groups reflect the interplay between structured clinical standards and patient specific demands—an effect widely recognised in SCI/D rehabilitation research (22).

2. Rehabilitation is effective, but treatment effects are heterogeneous.

International studies show considerable variation in recovery trajectories depending on lesion severity, demographic factors, comorbidities, and rehabilitation context (25, 26).

3. Cost effectiveness depends on patient profile.

Efficiency varies across subgroups, and tailored strategies improve value for both patients and health systems—an insight consistent with contemporary recommendations for precision rehabilitation and stratified economic evaluation (46, 51).

Together, these findings emphasise the importance of integrating clinical and economic considerations when designing rehabilitation pathways and evaluating the performance of specialised rehabilitation centres. They further align with broader health system calls for value-based resource allocation under growing demand and constrained cost environments (2).

2. Limitations and Future Research

Although this dissertation provides a thorough evaluation of service utilization, functional outcomes and cost-effectiveness in subacute SCI/D rehabilitation, it is important to consider several methodological and contextual limitations. First, reliance on a single-centre dataset may constrain external validity because rehabilitation pathways and outcomes vary across systems and settings (36). Second, the absence of repeated rehabilitation-outcome measures during rehabilitation limits capturing non-linear recovery trajectories, which typically require longitudinal assessment (25, 52). Third, psychosocial and environmental determinants—known to influence functioning—were only partly represented in routine data (53).

Future research should be conducted in multicentre settings to improve generalisability and benchmark organisational variability, incorporate longitudinal outcome measurement to characterise recovery dynamics more precisely, and consider a broader range of biopsychosocial determinants of functioning. In parallel, the systematic analysis of routine clinical data has become increasingly feasible due to improved availability and analytical capabilities, supporting more transparent and decision-relevant designs (30).

Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) offers methodological principles to structure and synthesise complex clinical information, ensuring interpretability, trustworthiness and clinical relevance of analytical outputs (54). Applied to rehabilitation analytics, XAI can reduce uncertainties inherent in information asymmetries during clinical decision-making and facilitate earlier identification of clinically meaningful trends in service patterns.

Furthermore, prospective studies that incorporate collaborative, iterative research processes—engaging clinicians, researchers and other stakeholders—enhance ecological validity and the clinical usefulness of model refinements (55). Finally, ethical, transparency-related and interpretability safeguards should be strengthened as rehabilitation research increasingly engages with complex data and algorithmic tools, to ensure responsible methodological innovation (8).

3. Conclusion

This dissertation offers an integrated evaluation of service utilization, functional improvement, and cost-effectiveness in subacute SCI/D rehabilitation. The findings indicate that rehabilitation is effective overall, while both outcomes and efficiency exhibit substantial variation across patient groups. Although rehabilitation is inherently resource-intensive, its clinical value is well established. Taken together, the results demonstrate that understanding how services are allocated—and how these allocations translate into functional outcomes and economic performance—is essential for optimising specialised rehabilitation.

Looking ahead, the results of this dissertation suggest several ways to strengthen rehabilitation research and practice, particularly by using routinely collected clinical data more systematically and by prioritising interpretability, transparency, and clinical relevance in analytical approaches. Improved analytical clarity could further enhance our understanding of the relationship between service patterns and outcomes, as well as the variation in efficiency across different patient profiles. In particular, integrating richer longitudinal data and harmonised multicentre information systems would allow for more robust modelling of recovery trajectories and benchmarking across settings.

Moreover, approaches that emphasise transparency, stakeholder engagement and human-centred principles when developing analytical tools may help to reduce uncertainties in service allocation, enhance confidence in data-informed decision-making processes and contribute to more personalised rehabilitation strategies. In this context, incorporating explainable AI principles where appropriate may facilitate clearer communication of analytical outputs while maintaining clinical relevance. Such methods have the potential not only to improve analytical trustworthiness but also to support clinicians in interpreting complex models in ways that strengthen patient-centred decision-making.

In essence, the prospective methodological and conceptual extensions highlighted above represent a natural continuation of the scientific foundation established in this dissertation. They offer pathways towards more refined, transparent and context-sensitive analyses that can strengthen decision-making processes and support the delivery of equitable, high-quality rehabilitation services in the future. Ultimately, advancing these analytical capabilities will help ensure that resource allocation aligns more closely with clinical need, therapeutic potential and societal value. These developments also align with the requirements of the Swiss Health Insurance Act (KVG) by reinforcing evidence on cost-effectiveness and strengthening the analytical basis for demonstrating appropriateness, efficiency, and clinical benefit. The Act mandates that reimbursed rehabilitation services must be effective, appropriate, and economically justified.

Bibliography

1. OECD. Health at a Glance 2023: OECD Indicators. OECD; 2023.
2. Cieza A, Causey K, Kamenov K, Hanson SW, Chatterji S, Vos T. Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease study 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet*. 2021;396(10267):2006-17.
3. Bickenbach J, Sabariego C, Stucki G. Beneficiaries of Rehabilitation. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2021;102(3):543-8.
4. Lakdawalla DN, Doshi JA, Garrison LP, Jr., Phelps CE, Basu A, Danzon PM. Defining Elements of Value in Health Care-A Health Economics Approach: An ISPOR Special Task Force Report [3]. *Value Health*. 2018;21(2):131-9.
5. Da Silva RB, Contandriopoulos AP, Pineault R, Tousignant P. A global approach to evaluation of health services utilization: concepts and measures. *Health Policy*. 2011;6(4):e106-17.
6. Cano-de-la-Cuerda R, Blazquez-Fernandez A, Marcos-Anton S, Sanchez-Herrera-Baeza P, Fernandez-Gonzalez P, Collado-Vazquez S, et al. Economic Cost of Rehabilitation with Robotic and Virtual Reality Systems in People with Neurological Disorders: A Systematic Review. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(6).
7. Vakulenko DV. Algorithmization and Optimization Models of Patient-Centric Rehabilitation Programs. *Cybernetics and Systems Analysis*. 2024;60(No. 5).
8. Bonnechere B, Timmermans A, Michiels S. Current Technology Developments Can Improve the Quality of Research and Level of Evidence for Rehabilitation Interventions: A Narrative Review. *Sensors (Basel)*. 2023;23(2).
9. Sakai K, Momosaki R, Hoshino E. Strategies for cost-effectiveness analysis of rehabilitation for older patients with acute heart failure. *Cost Eff Resour Alloc*. 2022;20(1):53.
10. Diop M, Epstein D. A Systematic Review of the Impact of Spinal Cord Injury on Costs and Health-Related Quality of Life. *Pharmacoecon Open*. 2024;8(6):793-808.
11. Kim M, Jeong W, Jang S, Park JH, Bae Y, Lee SW. Spinal Cord Injury Epidemiology and Causes: A Worldwide Analysis with 2050 Projections. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2025;13(20).
12. World Health Organization ea. Spinal cord injury 2024 [Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/spinal-cord-injury>].
13. Malekzadeh H, Golpayegani M, Ghodsi Z, Sadeghi-Naini M, Asgardoost M, Baigi V, et al. Direct Cost of Illness for Spinal Cord Injury: A Systematic Review. *Global Spine J*. 2022;12(6):1267-81.
14. Hodel J, Sabariego C, Galvis Aparicio M, Scheel-Sailer A, Seijas V, Ehrmann C. Revisiting functioning recovery in persons with spinal cord injury undergoing first rehabilitation: Trajectory and network analysis of a Swiss cohort study. *PLoS One*. 2024;19(2):e0297682.
15. Arora M, Craig AR. Special Issue-Spinal Cord Injuries: Advances in Rehabilitation. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(6).
16. Burns AS, Marino RJ, Kalsi-Ryan S, Middleton JW, Tetreault LA, Dettori JR, et al. Type and Timing of Rehabilitation Following Acute and Subacute Spinal Cord Injury: A Systematic Review. *Global Spine J*. 2017;7(3 Suppl):175S-94S.
17. Scheel-Sailer A, Lampart P, Selb M, Baumberger M, Gmunder HP, Sigrist-Nix D, et al. The Nottwil Standard-Development and Implementation of an International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health-Based Clinical Standard Assessment for Post-acute Rehabilitation After Newly Acquired Spinal Cord Injury. *Front Rehabil Sci*. 2021;2:720395.
18. Saa JP, Lipson-Smith R, White M, Davis A, Yang T, Wilde J, et al. Stroke Inpatient Rehabilitation Environments: Aligning Building Construction and Clinical Practice Guidelines Through Care Process Mapping. *Stroke*. 2023;54(11):2946-57.

19. Ackerman P, Morrison SA, McDowell S, Vazquez L. Using the Spinal Cord Independence Measure III to measure functional recovery in a post-acute spinal cord injury program. *Spinal Cord*. 2010;48(5):380-7.
20. McDaid D, Park AL, Gall A, Purcell M, Bacon M. Understanding and modelling the economic impact of spinal cord injuries in the United Kingdom. *Spinal Cord*. 2019;57(9):778-88.
21. Itzkovich M, Gelernter I, Biering-Sorensen F, Weeks C, Laramie MT, Craven BC, et al. The Spinal Cord Independence Measure (SCIM) version III: reliability and validity in a multi-center international study. *Disabil Rehabil*. 2007;29(24):1926-33.
22. Whiteneck G, Gassaway J, Dijkers M, Backus D, Charlifue S, Chen D, et al. The SCIRehab project: treatment time spent in SCI rehabilitation. Inpatient treatment time across disciplines in spinal cord injury rehabilitation. *J Spinal Cord Med*. 2011;34(2):133-48.
23. Taylor-Schroeder S, LaBarbera J, McDowell S, Zanca JM, Natale A, Mumma S, et al. The SCIRehab project: treatment time spent in SCI rehabilitation. Physical therapy treatment time during inpatient spinal cord injury rehabilitation. *J Spinal Cord Med*. 2011;34(2):149-61.
24. Teeter L, Gassaway J, Taylor S, LaBarbera J, McDowell S, Backus D, et al. Relationship of physical therapy inpatient rehabilitation interventions and patient characteristics to outcomes following spinal cord injury: the SCIRehab project. *J Spinal Cord Med*. 2012;35(6):503-26.
25. Alexander MS, Anderson KD, Biering-Sorensen F, Blight AR, Brannon R, Bryce TN, et al. Outcome measures in spinal cord injury: recent assessments and recommendations for future directions. *Spinal Cord*. 2009;47(8):582-91.
26. Nas K, Yazmalar L, Sah V, Aydin A, Ones K. Rehabilitation of spinal cord injuries. *World J Orthop*. 2015;6(1):8-16.
27. Palmer S, Torgerson DJ. Economic notes: definitions of efficiency. *BMJ*. 1999;318(7191):1136.
28. Willimsky U. Querschnittlähmung weltweit und im deutschsprachigen Raum: Zahlen und Fakten [Website]. *Der-Querschnitt.de*2021 [updated 09.07.2021; cited 2023 09.10.2023]. Available from: <https://www.der-querschnitt.de/archive/46568>.
29. Benchimol EI, Smeeth L, Guttman A, Harron K, Moher D, Petersen I, et al. The REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected health Data (RECORD) statement. *PLoS Med*. 2015;12(10):e1001885.
30. Gliedt JA, Spector AL, Schneider MJ, Williams J, Young S. A Description of Theoretical Models for Health Service Utilization: A Scoping Review of the Literature. *Inquiry*. 2023;60:469580231176855.
31. Rupp R, Biering-Sorensen F, Burns SP, Graves DE, Guest J, Jones L, et al. International Standards for Neurological Classification of Spinal Cord Injury: Revised 2019. *Top Spinal Cord Inj Rehabil*. 2021;27(2):1-22.
32. Roberts TT, Leonard GR, Cepela DJ. Classifications In Brief: American Spinal Injury Association (ASIA) Impairment Scale. *Clin Orthop Relat Res*. 2017;475(5):1499-504.
33. Organization WH. Guidance on the analysis and use of routine health information systems: rehabilitation module2022 08.07.2024 [cited 2024 08.07.2024]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/tools/routine-health-information-systems---rehabilitation-toolkit>.
34. Besson P. Branchenlösung REKOLE® – Betriebliches Rechnungswesen im Spital 2018.
35. AG S. SwissDRG – die Tarifstruktur in der stationären Akutsomatik. In: AG S, editor. 2023.
36. New PW, Reeves RK, Smith E, Townson A, Eriks-Hoogland I, Gupta A, et al. International retrospective comparison of inpatient rehabilitation for patients with spinal cord dysfunction epidemiology and clinical outcomes. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2015;96(6):1080-7.
37. Bladt M, Fuino M, Shemendyuk A, Wagner J. Modelling the burden of long-term care for institutionalised elderly based on care duration and intensity. *Annals of Actuarial Science*. 2023;17(1):83-117.

38. Schober P, Vetter TR. Count data in medical research: Poisson regression and negative binomial regression. *Anesth Analg*. 2021;132(5):1378-9.
39. Stoklosa J, Blakey RV, Hui FK. An overview of modern applications of negative binomial modelling in ecology and biodiversity. *Diversity*. 2022;14(5):320.
40. Yee TW. Vector generalized linear and additive models. Springer; 2007.
41. Ipsen JA, Pedersen LT, Draborg E, Bruun IH, Abrahamsen C, Viberg B. Cost-Effectiveness of Physical Rehabilitation and Care of Older Home-Dwelling Persons after Hip Fracture: A Systematic Review and Narrative Synthesis. *J Rehabil Med*. 2022;54:jrm00351.
42. Angerova Y, Marsalek P, Chmelova I, Gueye T, Uherek S, Briza J, et al. Cost and cost-effectiveness of early inpatient rehabilitation after stroke varies with initial disability: the Czech Republic perspective. *Int J Rehabil Res*. 2020;43(4):376-82.
43. Lanza ST. Latent Class Analysis for Developmental Research. *Child Dev Perspect*. 2016;10(1):59-64.
44. Furuta H, Mizuno K, Unai K, Ebata H, Yamauchi K, Watanabe M. Functional Independence Measure Subtypes among Inpatients with Subacute Stroke: Classification via Latent Class Analysis. *Prog Rehabil Med*. 2022;7:20220021.
45. Maaten Lvd, Hinton GE. Visualizing Data using t-SNE. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*. 2008;9:2579-605.
46. French MA, Roemmich RT, Daley K, Beier M, Penttinen S, Raghavan P, et al. Precision Rehabilitation: Optimizing Function, Adding Value to Health Care. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil*. 2022;103(6):1233-9.
47. Mishra S, Gosling J, Laplante-Levesque A, Zapata T, Azzopardi Muscat N. The need for rehabilitation services in the WHO European Region is substantial and growing. *Lancet Reg Health Eur*. 2023;24:100550.
48. Mold JW, Hamm RM, McCarthy LH. The law of diminishing returns in clinical medicine: how much risk reduction is enough? *J Am Board Fam Med*. 2010;23(3):371-5.
49. Wasiaak K, Frasunska J, Tarnacka B. Can the Initial Parameters of Functional Scales Predict Recovery in Patients with Complete Spinal Cord Injury? A Retrospective Cohort Study. *Diagnostics (Basel)*. 2024;14(2).
50. Jefferson T, Demicheli V, Vale L. Quality of systematic reviews of economic evaluations in health care. *JAMA*. 2002;287(21):2809-12.
51. Kurnianto AA, Kovacs S, Agnes N, Kumar P. Economic Evaluations of Rehabilitation Interventions: A Scoping Review with Implications for Return to Work Programs. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2025;13(10).
52. Maritz R, Fellinghauer C, Brach M, Curt A, Gmunder HP, Hopfe M, et al. A Rasch-Based Comparison of the Functional Independence Measure and Spinal Cord Independence Measure for Outcome and Quality in the Rehabilitation of Persons with Spinal Cord Injury. *J Rehabil Med*. 2022;54:jrm00262.
53. Geyh S, Kunz S, Muller R, Peter C, Swi SCISG. Describing functioning and health after spinal cord injury in the light of psychological-personal factors. *J Rehabil Med*. 2016;48(2):219-34.
54. Eke CI, Shuib L. The role of explainability and transparency in fostering trust in AI healthcare systems: a systematic literature review, open issues and potential solutions. *Neural Computing and Applications*. 2025;37(4):1999-2034.
55. Nitsch KP, Stipp K, Gracz K, Ehrlich-Jones L, Graham ID, Heinemann AW. Integrating Spinal Cord Injury - Quality of Life instruments into rehabilitation: Implementation science to guide adoption of patient-reported outcome measures. *J Spinal Cord Med*. 2021;44(6):940-8.